

Artificial Intelligence Threat Reporting and Incident Response System

D.8.1 Project Website

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation/ Acronym	Meaning
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICCS	Institute of Communication & Computer Systems
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The present deliverable is complementary to the delivered website and provides a brief description of the main features of the website that has been created for the IRIS project. The IRIS's website is one of the most important communication channels of the project. It will serve as a vital element of engagement with the identified key audiences. It will provide information about the project and will be constantly updated with the latest information regarding the progress and results of the project.

The website provides information about the project, such as a general description of the project, the project objectives, its consortium, project's events and news. Moreover, project presentations from events, scientific publications, all the public deliverables (once approved by the EC) and the executive summaries of all the confidential deliverables will be available on the website. In general, the website will present and explain in simple terms the project, its aim and why the key audiences and the general public should be interested in it.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Project Introduction

As existing and emerging smart cities continue to expand their IoT and AI-enabled platforms, this introduces novel and complex dimensions to the threat intelligence landscape linked with identifying, responding and sharing data related to attack vectors, based on emerging IoT and AI technologies.

IRIS's vision is to integrate and demonstrate a single platform addressed to CERTs/CSIRTs for assessing, detecting, responding to and sharing information regarding threats & vulnerabilities of IoT and AI-driven ICT systems. To achieve this, IRIS brings together experts in cybersecurity, IoT, AI explainability, automated threat detection, response, and recovery.

IRIS aims to help European CERTs/CSIRTs minimise the impact of cybersecurity and privacy risks as well as threats introduced by cyber-physical vulnerabilities in IoT platforms and adversarial attacks on AI-provisions and their learning/decision-making algorithms.

The IRIS platform will be demonstrated and validated on 3 highly realistic environments with the engagement of 3 smart cities (in Helsinki, Tallinn and Barcelona) along with the involvement of national CERTs/CSIRTs, and cybersecurity authorities.

The project will run from September 2021 to August 2024.

1.2 Deliverable Purpose

The purpose of the deliverable D8.1 Project Website is to give insight and detailed information regarding the IRIS website. In more detail, the main features of the IRIS website are presented, along with the design goals and important upgrades and adjustments needed to ensure easy navigation for different users.

1.3 Intended Readership

This deliverable is a public document and therefore it is disseminated both internally within the project consortium and externally to interested parties outside the project. The intended readership primarily comprises the members of the IRIS consortium, the European Commission (EC) and the IRIS Project Officer (PO).

2 THE IRIS WEBSITE

2.1 Concept and objectives

The IRIS website www.iris-h2020.eu has been developed since the beginning of the project. Furthermore, in September 2021 (M1) and even before the project's Kick off Meeting a static version of it was available to the public. The landing page (see ANNEX 1) included a short description of the project, its objectives, the project's details (call identifier, topic and duration), the project's social media, the consortium's partners, the project coordinator's contact details, the emblem of the EU and the acknowledgement text.

IRIS website is one of the most important communication tools for IRIS project, as it includes all the necessary information of the project and will be constantly updated with the latest news and updates. Moreover, it will serve as a key element of engagement with the identified key audiences and as the main channel to audiences outside the consortium, providing information on IRIS objectives, partners, publications and news. Finally, the website will be active at least for two years after the lifespan of the project.

2.2 Design approach

The website's design and layout align with the IRIS brand identity to create a well recognisable visual pattern. The IRIS website will significantly contribute to the wide dissemination of the project and therefore effort has been made to make it visually attractive, informative and easy to navigate. The website is dynamic and flexible in terms of structure and functionality in order to meet the project's changing requirements over time. Moreover, it is created with responsive web design techniques that make applicable and fitting to all devices.

2.3 Hosting and Running

The server is hosted in the Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) premises in Athens, Greece. The website has been developed in a mobile-friendly mode using WordPress Content Management System and is compatible with all available web browsers (Internet Explorer, Mozilla Firefox, Google Chrome, etc.). The Content Management System and the design are developed and customized by ICCS for the purposes of IRIS.

2.4 Site Map

The IRIS structure of the website has been created to display information about the project in a clear and accessible manner. For the reader's ease a diagram of the site map is provided in Figure 1. The comprised elements are presented in detail at the sections that follow.

Figure 1: IRIS Website Map

2.4.1 Home

The homepage is the entry point for site visitors by presenting important project information while using a simple and clear layout to focus on the project branding and facilitate navigation. It is presented below divided in four sections:

1. The header area contains the project logo on the left and the main upper navigation menu. Just below that, there is an eye-catching image, including also the acronym of the project and its complete title. Then, the user can quickly see some main aspects of the project namely the Call Identifier, the Topic, its Duration and the Consortium.
2. In the middle of the homepage, the most important information about the project is presented in two sections:
 - IRIS At a Glance, which serves as an introduction to the project and includes three buttons that lead to the Objectives, Concept and Impact of IRIS;
 - IRIS Pilot Use Cases, which serves as an introduction to the project's pilots and includes a button that leads to the detailed description of the three Pilot Use Cases.
3. Then, there is a section about IRIS latest news that leads to the News section, a subscription to the IRIS newsletter button and presentation of the logos of the consortium partners.
4. Finally, the footnote of the homepage includes the EU flag and the respective acknowledgment text, an imprint section, which includes a disclaimer notice and website information, the privacy policy, the cookies policy, links to the IRIS social media channels,

and the Project Coordinator's contact details. This footnote appears not only on the homepage but also on all website pages, ensuring EU funding visibility.

The layout of the IRIS website homepage is also shown in Figures 2,3 and 4.

Figure 2: IRIS homepage (1)

Figure 3: IRIS homepage (2)

Figure 4: IRIS homepage (3)

2.4.2 About

This section presents the IRIS identity through different subsections:

- **Concept:** This section presents the general concept of the IRIS project (figure 5).

Figure 5: About-Concept

- **Objectives:** This page provides a more detailed description of the project's main objectives (figure 6)

Figure 6: About-Objectives

- **Impact:** This section provides a detail description of the project's impacts (figure 7).

Figure 7: About-Impact

- **Consortium:** This section presents access to information regarding the consortium partners. Their official logos and their websites are provided (figure 8).

Figure 8: About-Consortium

2.4.3 What We Do

This section provides the visitor with information (objectives and short description) about each project WP (figure 9).

Figure 9: What We Do

2.4.4 Pilots

This section is divided in three subsections, each dedicated to each IRIS Pilot Use Case. There is information on each pilot demonstration, the scenarios and the city that will host them (figure 10).

Figure 10: Pilots

2.4.5 News

This page is comprised of two sub-pages: 'News', where the latest news regarding the project are published and 'Blog' in which short articles written by IRIS partners will be published.

2.4.6 Material Hub

This section presents material about the project addressed to media, other interested stakeholders and the general public. It is divided in five sub sections:

- Dissemination Material: the two versions of the IRIS brochure, poster and roll up banner will be available in downloadable format;
- Deliverables: all the public deliverables and the executive summaries of the confidential ones will be presented, once approved by the EC.;
- Media Center: all the press releases and press articles regarding the IRIS project;
- Newsletters: all the IRIS newsletters in downloadable format.
- Publications/Presentations: links from the OpenAIRE platform where the scientific papers will be uploaded, and presentations performed by the consortium partners in events.

2.5 Technical Aspects

IRIS website has been built with WordPress, using the theme: Avada. This theme allows the website manager to add, remove and change items directly from the front-end of the website. The following plugins were also used: Avada Builder, Avada Core, Contact Form 7, Duplicator, MC4WP: Mailchimp for WordPress, Post Type Switcher, Yoast Duplicate Post, Yoast SEO.

2.6 Privacy and Cookie Policy

The IRIS website is compliant with the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). To fulfil the requirements set by this Regulation, the website has implemented both a cookies policy and a privacy policy that are available on the Home page.

2.7 Website Update

ICCS being the Dissemination and Communication manager of the IRIS project is responsible for updating the website on a regular basis. The project website facilitates a broad range of communication activities. Project news regarding the participation of the consortium in events and progress and outcomes of the project will be posted systematically. Information on the project's deliverables and press activities will also be uploaded and updated frequently.

2.8 Website Monitoring

The website visiting tracker software Google Analytics has been added to the website and will provide at regular reporting times detailed insights into the IRIS website traffic. Google Analytics tools are useful as they allow measuring website traffic patterns; the number and duration of visits, the number of page views, the visitors' geographical location, correlation with the timing of the project events, etc. This information can be used to optimize the structure, the content and the design of the website to match its visitors' preferences. Moreover, Google Analytics ensures full GDPR compliance simultaneously with optimized analytics data – respecting both end-user privacy and the website's need for data and user insights.

3 CONCLUSIONS

The present document D8.1 Project Website has presented in detail the IRIS website delivered in month 2 of the project's lifespan. The website fully embeds the visual identity set at the beginning of the project and it is built following a structure that best contains and communicates the project's resources and findings. The end user is at the centre of the project, in all its aspects thanks to the clear and easy navigation. The current website represents a good and efficient starting point on which the project can progress and build itself.

ANNEX 1: IRIS LANDING PAGE

IRIS Details

<p>Call Identifier</p> <p>2020-SU-05-2020</p>	<p>Topic</p> <p>SU-0502-2020 Intelligent security and privacy management</p>	<p>Duration</p> <p>September 2021-August 2024 (36 Months)</p>	<p>Team</p> <p>19 EU partners</p>
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IRIS At a Glance

- ✓ IRIS's vision is to integrate and demonstrate a single platform addressed to CERTs/CSIRTs for assessing, detecting, responding to and sharing information regarding threats & vulnerabilities of IoT and AI-driven ICT systems
- ✓ IRIS aims to help European CERTs/CSIRTs minimise the impact of cybersecurity and privacy risks as well as threats introduced by cyber-physical vulnerabilities in IoT platforms and adversarial attacks on Alprovisions and their learning/decision-making algorithms
- ✓ The IRIS platform will be demonstrated and validated on 3 highly realistic environments with the engagement of 3 smart cities (in Helsinki, Tallinn and Barcelona) along with the involvement of national CERTs/CSIRTs and cybersecurity authorities
- ✓ The IRIS consortium consists of 19 European partners
- ✓ The project expands from September 2021 until August 2024

IRIS Objectives

- ✦ To identify the user, technical and business requirements and design the architecture of an AI threat reporting and incident response system to support the operations of CERTs/CSIRTs towards minimizing the impact caused by cybersecurity and privacy risks in IoT platforms and Alprovisions
- ✦ To analyse the relevant ethics principles and legal framework on privacy concerns, as well as to understand relevant stakeholders behaviour to identify the main legal, ethics and social enablers for the IRIS solution
- ✦ To design and implement an automated threat analysis framework capable of detecting and responding to cyber threats targeting IoT and AI-driven ICT systems, while exhibiting advanced recovery capabilities
- ✦ To develop a collaborative threat intelligence and information sharing toolset that allows ICT stakeholders and European CERTs/CSIRTs to create and seamlessly share context-rich information about cyber threats targeting IoT and AI-driven ICT systems
- ✦ To design and implement a data protection and accountability module to establish trust and enable the protection of data necessary for the successful operation of IoT and AI-enabled ICT systems
- ✦ To design and implement a virtual cyber range platform for training cybersecurity professionals to fight against adversarial AI and machine learning attacks
- ✦ To demonstrate and validate the integrated IRIS platform across three realistic pilot demonstrators in three smart cities
- ✦ To ensure wide communication and scientific dissemination of the IRIS results to the research, academic, and CERT/CSIRT community, efficient evaluation and business planning of the IRIS concepts and solutions to the market, and contribution of specific project results to relevant standardisation bodies

IRIS Consortium

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